
Workplace Stress among Employed Women: A Review of Causes, Consequences and Coping Strategy

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ABSTRACT

Women have become growing in prominence in the last several decades for the survival of any society or economy. Since women make up the majority of workers in every organization, they play a critical role in human resource development as well. Stress at the workplace is an extremely prevalent issue that affects organizations and women in the workforce. The purpose of this study is to reveal the causes, consequences and coping strategies for workplace stress among employed women. This study carried out an extensive investigation of the reciprocal relationship between women and workplace stress based on secondary data from various reliable sources. Working conditions, lack of autonomy, long workdays, resistance to job changes, excessive workloads, unpredictable work environments, and marital status are some of the factors that contribute to the prevalence of work-related stress and anxiety. Stress at workplace has a detrimental effect on workers and organizations, leading to psychological and physical side effects like headaches, mishaps, and emotional outbursts. It can also cause frustration, hypertension, and insomnia. Screening, counseling, support, mental health services, preventive programs, and lifestyle changes are the possible coping strategies for lessening workplace stress among employed women.

Keywords: Workplace Stress, Employed Women, Causes and Consequences, Coping Strategies

Introduction

Over the past few decades, stress has become an increasingly significant issue for organizations. Stress is a person's response to intense pressure to perform well in a competitive setting. There are extrinsic and intrinsic sources of work-related stress (Islam et al., 2012). Stress has an adverse effect on teaching faculty performance in the higher education sector because of the heavy workload associated with academic and research activities (Khalili, 2012). Workplace relationships, professional growth, organizational roles, and intrinsic aspects of the job are among the sources of stress (Greenberg, 2009). One's workload, poor communication skills, job insecurity, and conflicts within the organization can all be contributing factors to stress among educators.

Stressors are elements that lead to tension at the workplace, which affects a person's attitude and behavior there. Potential stressors can be broadly classified into three categories: environmental, organizational, and personal. A number of factors that frequently lead to professional stress among female employees are as follows: Long workdays without breaks, even at night; Resistance to job changes and organizational changes; Work overload; An unstable work environment; A lack of skill advancement for the position; Inadequate autonomy and excessive supervision; Unfavorable working conditions, such as a crowded workspace, noise, heat or cold, dirty air, dim lighting, hazardous or unsafe working conditions, etc (Kumar, 2023).

Management ineffectiveness such as lack of clarity of management policies and decision making, unsupportive relationship with coworkers and colleagues, competition among coworkers, lack of trust and harsh working relationship with coworker or colleague, feeling of limited opportunity for self-growth, and standing behind in corporate ladder are considered as the reasons of workplace stress among female employees (Faisal et al., 2019).

Women in the workforce experience stress as a result of having a family, job uncertainty, workplace culture, and high performance standards. Effective stress management requires teaching role occupants about the nature of stress, focusing stress in a constructive way, helping them recognize their strengths, and providing them with the tools they need to create coping mechanisms (Rajasekhar & Sasikala, 2013).

There exist multiple factors that may contribute to work-family conflict and the stress experienced by female employees. The number of hours worked outside the home, flexible or inflexible working hours, family size, and number of dependents all contribute to work-family conflict among married women employees. Married working women's psychological anguish and wellbeing are severely impacted by these variables (Balaji, 2014).

The major sources of stress among working women include perceived stress at work, low financial benefits, and stress resulting from insufficient safety and security (Singh, 2023). Due to family responsibilities, job insecurity, office culture, and high performance standards, working women face stress. They also concluded that role-holders should be empowered to develop coping mechanisms, learn about the nature of stress, and channel it for positive outcomes in addition to assisting them in identifying their own strengths (Essien, 2014).

Compared to their male counterparts, female educators are disproportionately more stressed out. The biggest sources of stress for academicians are long work hours, a lack of resources, and packed lectures. Daycare, child education, and the inability to spend enough time with friends and family are all very stressful problems for employed women (Kodavatiganti & Bulusu, 2011).

Previous study reveals that married women experience higher levels of stress than single women, and this stress is attributed to societal expectations, traditional tendencies, and the additional obligations and responsibilities that come with being a mother, wife, and housekeeper. The highest percentage of women experience significant levels of stress at work (Shikieri & Musa, 2012). The aim of this study is to review causes, consequences and coping strategies of stress of employed women at the workplace.

Methodology

The present study was conducted applying a thorough descriptive research method. It was primarily based on the secondary data. Secondary data has been obtained from numerous published sources such as textbooks, newspapers, journals, magazines and associated websites. In order to ensure a comprehensive analysis of causes, consequences and coping strategies of the stress of employed women in the workplace, previous study findings were also investigated. This study did not require ethical approval. All sources and publications were properly cited and acknowledged.

Discussion and Conclusion

Job stress has been identified as one of the most prevalent health issues in many businesses in Europe (Zoni et al., 2012) and around the world by an increasing corpus of research on occupational behavior and health (Kawakami & Haratani, 1999). Since job stress is one of the primary factors influencing working adults' mental health, it has received a lot of attention. Workplace demands that surpass an individual's perceived capacity to manage the circumstances effectively give rise to job stress and an adverse response (Hsieh & Tsai, 2019).

Figure 1: The evaluation of the Model of Work-related Stress' components and their interrelations (Ornek & Esin, 2020)

Married working women experience stress because of a variety of obligations to their families and employers, workplace harassment, excessive work hours, and an unbalanced work-life schedule. These conditions, which include persistent headaches, high blood pressure, and obesity, put working women under stress. Stress can be reduced by spending time with family, engaging in physical activity, and managing work and family obligations (Bhuvaneshwari, 2013). Because of cultural expectations, women suffer higher levels of work-family stress than men do, and as a result, they carry the brunt of higher levels of work-family stress. A number of variables potentially affect women workers' stress levels and work-life balance and the variables cause stress in female employees include the quantity and frequency of overtime, the number of hours worked per week, a rigid work schedule, an unsupportive boss, and an unwelcoming company culture (Balaji, 2014).

Among the effects of stress at workplace are:

- Stress at work has a detrimental effect on the employee as well as the organization. Stress at work can lead to a range of physical and emotional side effects, such as headaches, accidents, and emotional reactions including despair, fury, and anxiety (Faisal et al., 2019).
- The consequences for the organization encompass a decline in both quantity and quality of job output, elevated rates of absenteeism and employee turnover, and a surge in complaints and medical expenses (Kumar, 2023).

- Working women who experience high psychological demands, job strain, and low job control are more likely to suffer a stroke (Dhurandher & Janghel, 2015).
- Extreme stress at work might cause certain physical and psychological problems in an employee. Psychological challenges include frustration, whereas personal bodily challenges include hypertension, sleeplessness, and so forth. Numerous negative effects of stress on an organization include strained labor relations, a high risk of accidents, a poisonous work environment, animosity at work, and job dissatisfaction (Kumar, 2023).
- Working women's stress prevents them from focusing on household chores and culinary necessities. Three reasons contribute to women's stress levels: the aging of the population, the rise in divorce and single parenthood, and women's growing participation in the workforce (Dhanabhakym & Malarvizhi, 2014).
- Women experience stress due to a variety of issues, including stereotypes, discrimination, and having to play several roles in their careers (Singh, 2023).

Stress levels by gender and age are shown in Figure 2.

Sources: Elad, B ,2023

Figure 2: Stress levels by gender and age

Workplace Stress Statistics shown in Figure 3.

Sources: Elad, B ,2023

Figure 3: Workplace Stress Statistics shown in Figure 3.

Table 1 breaks down the stressors and potential outcomes into distinct categories for easier understanding.

Table: 1 the stressors and potential outcomes into distinct categories

Category	Stressors
Job-Related Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inadequate physical working conditions - Excessive workload - Tight deadlines - Exposure to physical danger, etc.
Organizational Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Unclear job responsibilities (role ambiguity) - Conflicting job demands (role conflict) - Responsibility for managing others - Boundary conflicts (internal/external), etc.
Career Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Over-promotion - Under-promotion - Lack of job security - Blocked career progression, etc.
Work Relationships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Poor relationships with supervisors, subordinates, or colleagues - Challenges in delegating tasks, etc.
Organizational Structure & Climate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of involvement in decision-making - Behavioral constraints (e.g., budgets) - Office politics - Limited consultation - Financial stress, etc.

Individual Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Anxiety levels - Neuroticism - Ambiguity tolerance - Type A personality traits, etc.
External (Non-Work) Factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Family issues - Life crises - Health problems: high blood pressure, high cholesterol, increased heart rate - Smoking - Depressive mood - Drinking as an escape - Job dissatisfaction - Lowered aspirations, etc.
Health Consequences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coronary heart disease - Mental health deterioration

Source: Michie, S. 2002

Stress Level in different categories and regions is shown in Figure.

Sources: Elad, B ,2023

Figure 4: Stress Level in different categories and regions

Table 2 provides a clear summary of individual stress management strategies and training approaches that help in mitigating workplace stress.

Table 2: Summary of individual stress management strategies and training approaches

Category	Details
Approach	- Combination of individual and organizational interventions to manage stress.
Individual Techniques	- Training and one-on-one psychological services (clinical, occupational, health, or counseling).
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance individual skills and resources. - Help individuals change their situation.
Phases in Stress Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active coping (fight/flight). - Rest (habituation) phases.
Training Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recognizing Stress: Becoming aware of early signs of stress. - Interruption: Using awareness to stop stress patterns before they escalate. - Analysis & Action: Analyzing stressful situations and creating plans to minimize stressors.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Active Coping & Relaxation: Developing coping and relaxation skills to create a buffer against stress. - Practice: Practicing these skills in low-stress environments to build confidence.
Training Courses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assertiveness training. - Communication skills development. - Time management. - Problem-solving techniques. - Effective management skills.

Source: Michie, S. ,2002.

By reviewing different literature, it is shown that there are different strategies for different categories for workplace stress. Strategies for workplace stress are shown in following Table 3.

Table 3: Strategies for workplace stress

Category	Strategies
Mindfulness Practices	Incorporating modern mindfulness techniques like yoga and meditation to improve focus and reduce stress.
Shock Therapy	NHS's introduction of shock therapy (delicate electric pulses) to treat stress, anxiety, and depression.
Vacations & Recreational Activities	Providing vacations, sports, and recreational activities to employees to prevent isolation and burnout.
Stress Management Counseling	Offering professional counseling to address individual psychological issues and workplace stress.
Workplace Restructuring	Restructure the workplace environment to better accommodate stress management.
Work Plan Adjustments	Establishing work schedules that align with the demands and responsibilities of the role.
Job Rotation	Clarify and implement job rotation to prevent monotonous and repetitive tasks.
Clear Job Descriptions & Advancement	Develop clear job descriptions and career advancement pathways.
Effective Communication Channels	Ensure open communication between employees and management.
Stress Management Workshops	Conduct regular stress management workshops for employees.
Compensation Reorganization	Reorganize compensation packages to provide adequate financial support.
Emotional & Task Support	Provide emotional support and assistance in fulfilling tasks and responsibilities.
Training Methods Improvement	Improve and modernize employee training techniques.
Performance Evaluation Systems	Focus on performance evaluations to identify strengths and weaknesses, and provide targeted training to reduce stress and enhance skill development.

Source: Sajid et al., 2021

Workplace stress among women is a multifaceted issue shaped by numerous factors. Although the causes may differ depending on the context, certain themes consistently emerge from research. Common contributors include excessive workloads, extended hours, poor work-life balance, and societal pressures. Additionally, organizational issues such as ineffective management, lack of support, and discrimination can heighten stress. Personal factors like family obligations, financial pressures, and health concerns can also add to the stress. The interaction of these elements often leads to negative outcomes for both individuals and businesses, such as increased absenteeism, reduced productivity, and harmful health effects.

Tackling workplace stress for women calls for a comprehensive strategy. Companies should focus on promoting work-life balance, employee support

systems, and fair treatment policies. On a personal level, women can adopt stress management strategies to help navigate challenges and protect their well-being. Identifying the sources of stress and applying effective solutions enables organizations to foster healthier, more supportive work environments for women.

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